

Fiscal Discipline and Sustainable Growth in Nigeria: A Reality Check for Developing Countries.

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ABSTRACT

The debate on the effectiveness of fiscal policy tool to achieve macroeconomic stability is prominent among scholars especially in light of recent happenings in Nigeria. However, available statistics shows that the prevalence of fiscal indiscipline has militated against the achievement of sustainable economic growth. Persistent rise in external debt and budget deficit has been identified as some of the indicators of fiscal indiscipline in Nigeria. This study reveals that there is the absence of sustainability going by the country's present fiscal stance. Thus, the study recommends that the government should maintain a healthy debt to GDP ratio which is one of the indicators of the debt repayment capacity of a borrowing nation. The government should reduce its budget deficits by cutting-down some items in its recurrent expenditure. Necessary reforms should be undertaken by the government to promote fiscal discipline.

Key Words: *Fiscal Policy, macroeconomic stability, fiscal discipline, External Debt*

1. INTRODUCTION

Fiscal policy implementation and its ability to effectively tinker with selected macroeconomic variables aimed at engendering sustainable economic growth is currently in the front burner of scholastic debate. This is in light of the worsening economic state of Nigeria as manifested in some economic variables which includes but is not limited to; debt crisis, unprecedented high levels of inflation, high unemployment rate, high exchange rate etc. The boom and bust phenomenon of oil prices and revenue upon which fiscal policy has been benchmarked in post-independent era, has been identified as the key problem (Ololade, 2019).

The entrenchment of fiscal discipline is a prerequisite for the attainment of targeted macroeconomic objectives such as; economic growth, price stabilization, reduction of unemployment and favorable balance of payment. Absence of fiscal discipline by the tiers of government (local, state and federal) has been identified as one of the challenges that have militated against the effectiveness of fiscal policy implementation in Nigeria. According to Bredino et al (2022), factors such as over-dependence on oil revenue, fiscal indiscipline, bureaucratic corruption, and poor governance reduces the potency of fiscal policy in addressing

key economic challenges and bringing about sustainable economic growth in Nigeria.

The Federal system of government that characterizes the Nigeria state makes it susceptible to fiscal indiscipline. As a decentralized system, funds are allocated to the local, state, and federal tiers of government. As will be seen in preceding sections of this paper, fiscal indiscipline stems more from the departments, ministries, and agencies of government. The activities of the aforementioned departments and ministries are fraught with high level of profligacy that tends to undermine any attempt of policy formulators to achieve targeted macroeconomic objectives, and ultimately jeopardize sustainable economic growth. Thus, the objective of this paper is to examine the impact of fiscal indiscipline on Nigeria's economic growth. To achieve the aforementioned objective, we begin with a brief review of relevant macroeconomic variables relating to the study subject in section (2). A critical analysis of the manifestations of fiscal indiscipline as well as its implication on the Nigerian economy was done in section (3) and (4) respectively. The conclusion and recommendations of the study was done in section (5).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Fiscal discipline is the ability of the government to maintain smooth financial operations and long-term fiscal health (Uwaleke, 2018). Put differently, fiscal discipline implies the ability of government to finance its current expenditure from its current revenue and thus, avoid persistent budget deficits. Though budget deficits may not necessarily be bad as it ensures short term benefits to the people. However, this comes at the cost of accumulating future tax burdens in the long run (Musgrave 1989). For instance, when George W. Bush moved into the White House in 2001, he reduced taxes, which helped end the recession but also contributed to an emergence of budget deficit (Mankiw, 2008).

Yet another definition of fiscal discipline is the spending by the various government agencies within the limits stipulated in the appropriation bill. Put differently, these agencies should spend on legislatively intended items or purposes. It is in tandem with the aforementioned that Pullah et al. (2020) concludes that government should re-evaluate her expenditures (capital and recurrent) to ensure that funds are only expended on projects that will yield maximum socio-economic impact to the economy. Oil revenue volatility and uncertainty obviously affects the potency of fiscal policy, especially in an oil dependent country like Nigeria. This is manifested in the high volatility of revenue and expenditure, which is largely reflected in oil price fluctuation. Thus, the need for the conceptualization and implementation of appropriate fiscal rule to curtail recurrent fiscal deficits and public debt aimed at achieving sustained economic growth (Baunsgaard, 2003).

The Nigerian economy is largely dependent on the oil revenue so much so that its annual budgets are prepared on the basis of projected crude oil prices which is highly volatile, thus, in the event of a fall in the price of oil, or reduction in demand, budget deficits becomes inevitable.

The campaign for the entrenchment of an interventionist approach to resolving economic problems was led by John Maynard Keynes. Unlike the classical economists, he believed that the manipulation of the components of aggregate demand and supply is the fulcrum upon which every economic system rests (Keynes 1936). According to him, the government embarks on expansionary fiscal policy to boost demand and stimulate the economy in times of economic downturn. In such instances persistent budget deficit is expected. However, theoretically, the aforementioned expansionary policy may turn out to be counter-productive for two reasons; first, the rise in interest rate resulting from the increase in government borrowing, second is the crowding out of private investors as a result of the crowding-out effect. Despite the aforementioned assertion, empirical studies have shown that though the rise in interest rate, and the crowding-out effect play a part in reducing the multiplier effects of the expansionary fiscal stance of the government; the major challenge facing the Nigeria fiscal system are; over dependence on oil revenue by the Nigeria government, fiscal indiscipline, bureaucratic corruption, and poor governance (Bredino et al., 2022).

3. MANIFESTATIONS OF FISCAL INDISCIPLINE IN NIGERIA

Persistent Budget Deficits:

It is rare to find a government that does not have a budget deficit at one point or the other. This is because economic indicators or variables are unpredictable, especially since macroeconomic policies are implemented based on certain underlying assumptions about the economy that most times may be unrealistic (Bredino et al., 2022). In such circumstances, policy formulators may momentarily choose to adopt an expansionary policy. Therefore, contrary to Musgrave's definition, budget deficits may not necessarily be dubbed "fiscal indiscipline" especially if there are evidences to show that the borrowed funds were judiciously utilized.

The trend in Nigeria show that government at all levels run persistent budget deficits. They tend to have insatiable appetite for spending without considering the economic implication of their actions. It is in this regard, that the Bredino et al.,(2022) posited, that the major challenge of public finance is how to control and set a limit to public spending and peg it within an acceptable range that is economically viable.

According to Wagner's theory of government expenditure, giving some inherent inextricable economic variables that naturally exhibit a growing trend such as; population, and inflation it may be difficult to contract public expenditure in avoiding a budget deficit (Wagner, 1980). Besides, several studies have shown that there is a positive and significant relation between public expenditure and economic growth (Chandana, Adamu, & Musa, 2021; Baldacci, Clement, Gupta, & Cui, 2008)

Figure 1. Government Revenue and Expenditure Trend (1981 – 2021)

Source: CBN Statistical Bulletin 2021

Figure 1 above shows the revenue and expenditure trend of the Nigerian government for 40 years (1981 -2021). The expenditure component consists of both recurrent and capital expenditure. Also, government revenue consists of both oil and non-oil revenue sources. As seen from the graph, there have been persistent rise in both revenue and expenditure in the period under review; however, the rise in government revenue is more than proportionate to that of government expenditure. The shape of the government expenditure curve is in tandem with Wagner's law of government expenditure which stipulates that there is the tendency for government expenditure at all levels to increase.

Increasing External Debt:

Increasing external debt is a major manifestation of fiscal indiscipline in Nigeria (Uwaleke, 2018). Persistent government budget deficits are financed through borrowing. Most times these funds are gotten at very high rate of interest. Debts are incurred when countries fall short of funds to meet their statutory needs. According to Sulaiman et al. (2012), the lack of sufficient financial resource in developing countries is the main rationale behind the compounding external debt. However, contrary to the above claim other factors such as; fiscal rascality, corruption, and absence of leadership could account for the high debt profile of developing countries (Bredino et al., 2022).

The dual gap analysis framework posits that development is a function of investment and that the available domestic savings in developing nations are insufficient to invest. Thus, the justification for external borrowing to stimulate economic growth especially in light of insufficient financial resources (Oloyede, 2002; Hameed et al, 2008). Yet another justification for external borrowing is that posited by Soludo (2003). According to him, the main macroeconomic reasons for borrowing are; the financing of high investment or higher consumption to circumvent budget constraint. By implication, the original intent of borrowing ought to be the alleviation of poverty and promotion of sustainable development. However, there is a certain threshold or limits for borrowing beyond which the economy becomes adversely affected. The huge debt burden crowds out investment and growth. The aforementioned has been the case in Nigeria with the humongous external debt values and very high debt burden.

As at March 31st 2022, Nigeria’s total public debt was N41, 604,507.45 million out of which N16,617,190.74 million accounts for total external debt, N24,986,886.71 million accounts for total domestic debt i.e. debts accumulated by states including the FCT (DMO, 2022). There is very high consensus among scholars and economic observers that huge external debt has negative impact on economic growth (Mojekwu and Ogege, 2012).

Figure 2: Comparative Statistics of Debt Profile of Selected African
 Source: IMF dataset

Figure 2 above is a diagrammatic view of the debt profile of selected African countries including; Nigeria, Angola, Cameroun, South Africa, Ghana, Cote –Ivoire, and Rwanda. As seen, Nigeria has the highest debt profile for the 2012-2018. As stated earlier high external debt profile is partly a manifestation of fiscal indiscipline. This goes to show that there is high level of fiscal

indiscipline in the country in relation to other countries.

4. IMPLICATIONS OF FISCAL INDISCIPLINE

The persistent growth in the real stock of government debt over time as evident in the Nigeria economy is testament to the fact that its fiscal policy is not sustainable. The consistent adoption of an expansionary fiscal stance i.e. persistent rise in government expenditure in relation to taxation (revenue) has resulted in widening fiscal deficit (Sharon & Shaniska, 2020).

The consequence of the widening fiscal deficits will naturally result to increasing debt burden. The aforementioned phenomenon is the case in Nigeria where the government rather than seek out way to internally generate funds to finance its budget deficits, will run to other foreign entities to borrow. The persistent growth in the real stock of government borrowing is an indication that our present fiscal policy stance is not sustainable and is inimical to economic growth.

Table 1: Nigeria's Total Public Debt Portfolio As at March 2022

	Debt Category	Amount Outstanding (US\$'M)	Amount Outstanding (N'M)	% of Total
A.	Total External Debt	39,969.19	16,617,190.74	39.94%
B.	Total Domestic Debt	60,100.70	24,986,866.71	60.06%
	FGN Only	48,452.26	20,144,027.72	48.42%
	State & FCT	11,648.44	4,842,838.00	11.64%
C.	Total Public Debt (A + B)	100,069.89	41,604,057.45	100%

Source: Debt Management Office (2022)

Table 1 above is evidence of the magnitude of the increasing debt portfolio of the Nigeria. As at March 2022 the total outstanding public debt of the country (external & domestic) amounts to N41,604,057.45 million. The most annoying aspect of this argument is that over 70% of the debts incurred are expended on recurrent expenditure.

5. CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATION

The unprecedented rise in Nigeria external debt and persistent budget deficits show that there is a high degree of fiscal indiscipline. No economy can achieve its targeted macroeconomic objectives in the absence of fiscal discipline. The widening fiscal deficits and resultant accumulation of the country's debt burden is inimical to sustainable economic growth. Thus, it is recommended that

1. The government should maintain a healthy debt to GDP ratio which is one of the indicators of the debt repayment capacity of the borrowing nation.
2. The government should ameliorate its budget deficits by cutting-down some items in its recurrent expenditure.

3. Necessary reforms should be undertaken by the government to promote fiscal discipline

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APPENDIX 1

Table A1: Summary of Federal Government Finance

PERIOD	GOVT RECURRENT EXPENDITURE (₦ Billions)	GOVT CAPITAL EXPENDITURE (₦ Billions)	TOTAL GOVT. EXP. (₦ Billions)	TOTAL GOVT. REV (₦ Billions)
1981	4.85	6.57	11.41	13.3
1982	5.51	6.42	11.92	11.4
1983	4.75	4.89	9.64	10.5
1984	5.83	4.10	9.93	11.3
1985	7.58	5.46	13.04	15.1
1986	7.70	8.53	16.22	12.6
1987	15.65	6.37	22.02	25.4
1988	19.41	8.34	27.75	27.6
1989	25.99	15.03	41.03	53.9
1990	36.22	24.05	60.27	98.1
1991	38.24	28.34	66.58	101.0
1992	53.03	39.76	92.80	190.5
1993	136.73	54.50	191.23	192.8
1994	89.97	70.92	160.89	201.9
1995	127.63	121.14	248.77	460.0
1996	124.29	212.93	337.22	523.6
1997	158.56	269.65	428.22	582.8
1998	178.10	309.02	487.11	463.6
1999	449.66	498.03	947.69	949.2
2000	461.60	239.45	701.05	1,906.2
2001	579.30	438.70	1,018.00	2,231.6
2002	696.80	321.38	1,018.18	1,731.8
2003	984.30	241.69	1,225.99	2,575.1
2004	1,110.80	351.25	1,462.05	3,920.5
2005	1,321.30	519.47	1,840.77	5,547.5
2006	1,390.20	552.39	1,942.59	5,965.1
2007	1,589.27	759.28	2,348.55	5,727.5
2008	2,117.36	960.89	3,078.25	7,866.6
2009	2,127.97	1152.80	3,280.76	4,844.6
2010	3,109.44	883.87	3,993.31	7,303.7
2011	3,314.51	918.55	4,233.06	11,116.8
2012	3,325.16	874.70	4,199.86	10,654.7
2013	3,689.10	1108.39	4,797.49	9,759.8
2014	3,426.94	783.12	4,210.06	10,068.9
2015	3,831.95	818.35	4,650.30	6,912.5
2016	4,160.11	653.61	4,813.71	5,616.4
2017	4,779.99	1242.30	6,022.28	7,444.8
2018	5,675.20	1682.10	7,357.30	9,551.7

2019	6,997.20	2289.00	9,286.19	10,262.3
2020	8,188.81	1614.89	9,803.70	9,276.1
2021	9,145.16	2522.47	11,667.62	10,755.4

Source: Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin 2021